

Statistical States and Their Relationship to Constraints Part II

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In Part I, we argue that in statistics, probability is often taken to be proportional to the number of states consistent with some constraints. For example, for the case of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas of n particles with total energy E , the constraint is on energy and so one considers various energy configurations. In other words, energy is physically being distributed because this is what changes in a collision. One may argue that $e=pp/2m$, so momentum is also changing, but the equilibrium problem is associated with distributing energy, not momentum. The equilibrium process gives rise to a probability function in terms of the constraint variable, in this case single particle energy, i.e. $e=pp/2m$. The fact that one may write energy in terms of the magnitude of momentum does not mean that one is dealing with the change in the momentum vector. Such a change is different because it includes orientation changes with no magnitude change. In other words, the constraint dictates how changes to a single particle variable occur (e.g. single particle energy) and this determines the states available.

We stress this point, because it is possible to write the constraint for the Maxwell-Boltzmann gas as: $\sum_{i=1,n} p(i)p(i) = 2mE$ where one has n particles moving in 1-dimension, so $p(i)$ is the momentum of the i th particle. Mathematically this is an equation of an n -sphere. If one sets $p(n)$ to a particular value: $\sum_{i=1,n-1} p(i)p(i) = 2mE - p(n)p(n)$. This is the equation of an $n-1$ sphere. In (1), it is argued that one may think of $\{p(i)\}$ as constituting an $n-1$ vector. We argue against this because there is no physical constraint of a vector in this problem. This is a mathematically created constraint. In collisions, single particle energy changes and this creates the equilibrium. In other words, one considers 2-body elastic scattering and ignores momentum completely in obtaining $\exp(-e/T)$. Thus, on physical grounds, we argue that one does not have a physical vector and should not use a constraint linked with such a vector. Arguing that $P(E-p(n)p(n))$ is proportional to the surface area of an $n-1$ sphere makes use of a constraint which is not part of the physical distribution process of the problem. It is a stronger constraint, so to speak, and leads to fewer allowable states, i.e. $(E-e)$ power $(n-3)/2$ versus $(E-e)$ power $(n-2)$. One does not physically have a vector constrained to a surface.

One may, however, use the procedure of (1) to describe the probability of a vector component for an n -vector. This is a different problem from the Maxwell-Boltzmann one. The result for $n=2$ for the general result of (1) yields the probability of a vector component (p_x, p_y) for a fixed magnitude as given in (3).. A physical vector may be associated with motion constrained to a surface.

Thus, we argue that one must be careful about interpreting constraints in a problem and determining states. Given a constraint in one variable, it may be written in terms of another, e.g. an energy constraint may be written in terms of momentum squared of a number of particles, but to argue that the momentum components of different 1-dimensionally moving particles constitute a vector is introducing a constraint which does not exist in the problem.

Constraints and Variables

Imagine that one only has a concept of momentum (not energy). One may argue that a gas of particles involves 2-body collisions. Momentum (which is a vector) must be conserved in such collisions, but arguing that the collisions must be elastic, i.e. $p(1)p(1) + p(2)p(2) = p(3)p(3) + p(4)p(4)$, where one has one dimensional moving particles and p is momentum, is a different constraint. It is a constraint on the magnitude of momentum. One must decide if it is the conservation of momentum (vector) which holds for any interaction, or the elastic constraint which is key to equilibrium. If equilibrium is about energy distribution, one would expect that:

$$P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_3)P(e_4) \text{ for } e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4 \quad ((1))$$

It seems that the elastic condition is the driver of equilibrium and this is a constraint on the distribution of the quantity:

$$\text{Sum over } i=1,n \quad p(i)p(i) = B = (2mE) \quad ((2))$$

Thus it is a quantity B which is distributed and creates equilibrium. Then, ((2)) may be written as:

$$\text{Sum over } i=1,n \quad b(i) = B \quad ((3))$$

In other words, the concept of momentum has disappeared and one has replaced it with a quantity $b(i)$ which is a scalar for particle (i) and adds to a total B . This is the constraint one must work with and so one may consider changes in $b(i)$ which lead to different allowable states. For example, one may have a set $\{b(i)\}$ which satisfies ((3)). Changing $b(i)$ to $b(i) + db(i)$ yields new states provided:

$$\text{Sum over } i \quad db(i) = 0 \quad ((4))$$

States are created due to changes in $b(i)$ and have nothing to do with the underlying $p(i)p(i)$ as far as the probability distribution is concerned. This is a weaker constraint, so to speak, as one ignores the underlying momentum. Maximizing the number of states associated with $b(i)$ (i.e. e_i , the single particle energy) leads to $\exp(-e/T)$, i.e. the Maxwell-Boltzmann relationship. It is at this point that one may go back to the momentum picture and find the momentum states which yield the same e_i value, i.e. in 3-dimensions:

$$C \, dp_x \, dp_y \, dp_z \quad ((5))$$

In (1), the following argument is made for an n particle 1-dimensional gas. Consider ((2)) with $p(n)$ having a fixed value. Then:

$$\text{Sum over } i=1,n-1 \quad p(i)p(i) = B - p(n)p(n) = B_1 \quad ((6))$$

((6)) represents an $n-1$ sphere, with $p(i)$ as components of an $n-1$ vector. This, however, is a mathematical picture. There is no physical vector in this problem. One is only interested in changes in $p(i)p(i)$, which adds to a constant. (1) argues that probability $P(p(n)p(n))$ is proportional to the surface area of the $n-1$ sphere. This, however, involves a constraint of vectors lying on a surface of a sphere which is not the original constraint of the problem ((6)). In other words, one introduces a different constraint which is consistent with ((6)). We argue that this describes a different physical problem. In other words, we caution against using a constraint which maps or is associated with the constraint given in the problem

Probability of an n-Vector

Consider an n -vector $\{ p(i) \}$ where $p(i)$ are now vector components of a physical vector (which may be measured). In such a case, the physical constraint is:

$\{ p(i) \}$ lie on the surface of an n -sphere ((7))

Physically, one changes from one p -vector to another on the sphere, which means the magnitude is kept constant. This is consistent with the constraint:

Sum over $i=1, n$ $p(i)p(i) = B$ ((8))

, but more is “happening” with a vector.

We argue, however, that the constraint ((8)) simply states that one has n numbers which add to a number B . It says nothing about vectors unless one adds the extra condition that $p(i)$ represents the component of a physical vector. This then is the real constraint and changes occur by changing the vector components such that the magnitude is constant. ((8)) is only part of the constraint.

In such a case, the approach of (1) holds. It describes the probability of a component of a vector. In particular, consider a $p(n)p(n)$. Then:

Sum over $i=1, n-1$ $p(i)p(i) = B - p(n)p(n)$ ((9))

1 argues that the $n-1$ vector of $p(i)$'s lies on the surface of an $n-1$ sphere and that probability is proportional to this surface area.

1 develops the general formula: $P(p) dp = C (E - pp/2m)^{\text{power } (n-3)/2}$ ((10))

Using $n=2$, one obtains: $P(p) dp = C / \text{sqrt}(E - pp/2m)$ ((11))

This matches the probability for a vector component given in (3).

((9)), with no concept of a vector, is a weaker constraint and is shown to lead to a probability of $(E - e)^{\text{power } (n-2)}$.

Thus, we argue that one must be careful in determining the exact constraint which exists in a problem. Using a partial constraint such as ((8)) to describe a vector does not suffice. It yields a probability proportional to $(E-e)$ power $(n-2)$ as shown in (2), not the vector result ((10)) of (1) which is associated with a stronger constraint than ((8)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that sometimes one constraint may be associated with another. For example, consider a vector $\{p(i)\}$ with a fixed magnitude. One has a clear concept of a vector with different $p(i)$ values leading to different points on a sphere. The magnitude squared of the vector is given by: $\sum_{i=1,n} p(i)p(i) = B$. This equation, however, is only part of the vector constraint, we argue. It represents a summation of numbers, i.e. $\sum_{i=1,n} b(i) = B$. This equation, by itself, does not fully describe a vector. It is less restrictive. It may be associated with changes in $b(i)$ such that B remains constant. To describe a vector, one must consider the vector tip as lying on a surface of a sphere, which is a strong constraint, we argue.

Thus simply using the constraint $\sum_{i=1,n-1} b(i) = B - b(n)$ leads to a probability $P(b(n))$ proportional to $(B-b(n))$ power $(n-2)$. The more restrictive constraint of a vector leads to the result of (1), i.e. $P(b(n))$ proportional to $(B-b(n))$ power $((n-3)/2)$ which represents the probability of a 2-vector for $n=2$. This result of (1) is obtained by assuming that the $n-1$ vector $\{p(i)\}$ ($p(n)$ removed) lies on an $n-1$ sphere. For a vector, this is a true constraint, but if one does not have a vector, $\sum_{i=1,n-1} b(i) = B - b(n)$ is a weaker constraint leading to more states.

References

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